

Indoor Air Quality Monitoring System for Underground Subway Stations

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The confined space occupied by the underground subway system can accumulate the pollutants entering from the outside in addition to those generated within the system. Therefore, it is likely that the subway system in the Seoul metropolitan area contains different types of hazardous pollutants due to the old ventilation and accessory systems [3, 6].

Radon is a natural, inert, invisible, odorless, chemically inactive, and radioactive gas emitted by the earth. Because it is inert and does not chemically bond to elements, it is released from soil into the atmosphere. Because inhaling radon and its radioactive-decay products cause irradiation of lung tissue, prolonged exposure to a high concentration of radon significantly increases the risk of developing cancer [7,8].

The IAQ in the subway stations can be affected by many factors, such as the number of passengers, the outside conditions and the natural ventilation rate [9, 10], etc. The management and monitoring of IAQ in subway stations have become an important issue of public interest [11-13]. Some environmental sensors are important for monitoring IAQ in subway systems and they provide the data needed for continuous online implementation. Sometimes, these sensors in subway stations suffer from poor quality of data and the unreliability of the sensor due to the highly deteriorated and polluted environment, which may cause the measuring instruments installed for monitoring to malfunction. The quality of the online measurement can determine the failure or success of IAQ monitoring and assessment.

ABSTRACT

The IAQ has been recognized as a significant factor in the determination of the health and welfare of people. In this study, the air quality monitoring system based on environmental sensors was implemented to display and record the data on PM₁₀, CO₂, radon concentration, temperature, and humidity. In addition, a USN monitoring system is implemented to display and record the environmental sensor data measured in an underground subway station. To transmit and receive these measured sensor data, Wi-Fi wireless communication is applied.

KEYWORDS: IAQ, environmental sensor, PM₁₀, CO₂, radon concentration, temperature, humidity, USN

I. INTRODUCTION

The IAQ (Indoor Air Quality) has been recognized as a significant factor in the determination of the health and welfare of people [1]. The Korea Ministry of Environment (KMOE) enforced the IAQ act to control some pollutants, including PM₁₀, CO₂ in indoor environments. Out of these, the IAQ standard for PM₁₀ concentration is 150 µg/m³. The IAQ is critical not only in buildings but also in underground areas and public transportation systems. Much effort has been made for the improvement of the IAQ in subway stations [2-5].

Among the various types of indoor environments, underground subway stations have especially unique features.

In this study, the air quality monitoring system based on environmental sensors was implemented in an underground subway station to display and record the data on PM₁₀, CO₂, radon concentration, temperature, and humidity. In addition, a Wi-Fi wireless communication was applied in order to transmit and receive these measured sensor data.

II. Environmental Sensors

2.1. Radon sensors:

The RD200M is the new innovative fastest radon sensor, which has the highest sensitivity, 30 cph/pCi/L on the market today. This sensor is optimized for the IAQ monitor, air purifier, radon detector and auto ventilation system. A breakthrough in FTLAB's patent technology which received a New Excellent Technology certification in 2015, the RD200M uses a dual probe structured pulsed ionization chamber and a special high impedance differential amplifier circuit to offer the highest signal to noise ratio. It effectively detects the secondary charges which were generated from collisions with air and α-particle caused by radon or radon's progeny. The accuracy and precision of the RD200M are ±10% at 10pCi/L, which has been tested by the international standard Radon Testing Laboratory in KTL. Each sensor has been individually calibrated by equipment which is already calibrated to traceable international standards. Fig. 1 shows the ion chamber-type radon counter: RD200, made by FTLAB, Korea. Table 1 shows the specifications of the RD200.

Fig.1. Ion chamber-type radon counter: RD200

2.2. PM₁₀ sensors: Particulate matter with an aerodynamic diameter of less than 10 μm (PM₁₀) is one of the major pollutants in subway environments. The PM₁₀ concentration in the underground areas should be monitored to protect the health of the commuters in the underground subway system. Seoul Metro and Seoul Metropolitan Rapid Transit Corporation measure several air pollutants regularly. As for the PM₁₀ concentration, generally, measuring instruments based on the β-ray absorption method are used. In order to keep the PM₁₀ concentration below a healthy limit, the air quality in the underground platform and tunnels should be monitored and controlled continuously. The PM₁₀ instruments using light scattering method can measure the PM₁₀ concentration every once in several seconds. However, the accuracy of the instruments using light scattering method still has not been proven since they measure the particle number concentration rather than the mass concentration.

Table1. Specifications of RD200

Descriptions	RD200 is a real-time smart radon detector for homeowner which has the high sensitivity 0.5cpm/pCi/L, about 20~30 times more than conventional radon detector by FTLAB's high stable circuit technology
Type	pulsed ion chamber 200cc
First reliable data out	< 60min
Data interval	10min update (60min moving average)
Sensitivity	0.5cpm/pCi/L at 10pCi/L (30cph/pCi/L)
Operating range	10~40 °C, RH<90%
Range	0.1~99.99pCi/L
Precision	<10% at 10pCi/L
Accuracy	<±10% (min. error <±0.5pCi/L)
Power	DC 12 ± 0.1V, 65mA (12V DC adapter)
Size	Φ80(mm) x 120(mm), 240g
Data Communication	Bluetooth LE (Android/iOS)
Data log	max 1year(1h step)
Display	0.96 inch OLED

In order to continuously measure the PM₁₀ concentrations in the underground subway stations, Airstest PM2500 (Heyoka solutions, USA) was installed on the tunnel at a subway station of Seoul metro line number 1. The specifications of the PM measuring instrument Airstest PM2500 which is shown in Fig. 2 are listed as follows :

- Sampling Method: Laser particle counter;
- Particle Channels: 1.0-5.0 μm, 5.0+ μm;
- Flow Rate: 0.06 cfm nominal;
- Concentration Limit: Coincidence loss of less than 10% at 1,000,000 particles/cubic foot;
- Display Format: Particles/cubic foot (divided by 100) averaged over 1 minute;
- Data Storage: 60 minutes of minute averages, 24 hours of hourly averages, 30 days of daily averages;
- Dimensions: 7.5 x 5.0 x 3.5 inches;
- Weight: Approximately 12 oz;
- Power: 9VDC, 400mA, 110VAC plug-in transformer provided;

Fig.2. The PM measuring instrument Airstest PM2500 installed at a subway station

2.3. Temperature and humidity sensors:

Seoul Metropolitan Rapid Transit Corporation measures temperature and humidity as well as PM₁₀ and CO₂ in the subway stations regularly. Temperature and humidity can also be used for the analysis and prediction of IAQ in a subway station. As for temperature and humidity sensors, the SHT11 manufactured by Sensirion was chosen in this study. It is a single chip relative humidity and temperature multi-sensor module, comprising of a calibrated digital output. It is coupled to a 14-bit analog to digital converter and the 2-wire serial interface and internal voltage regulation, which allow easy and fast system integration. The pin assignment of SHT11 is shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 4 shows that the SHT11 is connected to the ATmega 128L CPU board, which transmits temperature and humidity data to the desktop PC using the RS232C interface.

Fig.3. Pin assignment of the temperature and humidity sensor SHT11.

Fig.4. The temperature and humidity sensor SHT11 connected to the ATmega 128L CPU board.

2.4. NDIR CO₂ sensors:

Recently, the monitoring of carbon dioxide (CO₂) has been considered very important for passengers and employees in underground subway stations due to the health risks associated with carbon dioxide exposure. For instance, headache, sweating, dim vision, tremors and loss of consciousness are caused by exposure to high CO₂ concentration for a long time.

CO₂ gas sensors being used presently can be divided into two types. The first one is the NDIR (Non-Dispersive Infrared) method and the second one is a chemical method. They are commonly available for monitoring CO₂ concentrations indoors. However, chemical CO₂ sensors have many limitations that prevent their application to a variety of practical fields. The obvious drawbacks of chemical CO₂ sensors are short-term stability and low durability. This is because chemical sensors are easily deteriorated by heterogeneous gases and minute particles in the ambient polluted air. On the other hand, since the NDIR method uses

the physical sensing principle, such as gas absorption at a particular wavelength, NDIR sensors are more advanced in terms of long-term stability and accuracy during CO₂ measurement. Hence, NDIR CO₂ sensors are the most widely applied for real-time monitoring of CO₂ concentration. The NDIR CO₂ sensor H-550 manufactured by ELT Co. Ltd, Korea and its connection to ATmega 128L MPU board is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig.5. NDIR CO₂ sensor connected to Atmega 128L MCU board

2.5. IAQ monitoring system:

This study presents the implementation of an IAQ monitoring system, which uses sensor modules for measuring PM₁₀, CO₂, radon concentration, temperature, humidity and a data processing module with Wi-Fi communication capabilities for the transmission and management of the measurement results. The need for air quality measuring over large underground subway areas, such as waiting rooms, platforms and tunnels, necessitates wireless connectivity for the measuring device. Wireless sensor networks represent a vast and active research area in which a large number of applications have been proposed, including indoor air quality monitoring and control, structural health monitoring, and traffic monitoring. Fig. 6 shows an air quality management system for subway stations. Fig. 7 shows the web page of the air quality management system.

Fig.6. Air quality management system

Fig.7. Web page of the air quality management system

The PM₁₀, CO₂, temperature, humidity, and radon concentration data which were measured in the tunnel of a subway station for 5 days are shown in Fig. 8. The PM₁₀, CO₂, temperature, and humidity were recorded at a sampling interval of 30 sec. On the other hand, the radon concentration was recorded at a sampling interval of 1 hour. As for the PM₁₀ concentration, it was mainly over 150 μg/m³, which was the KMOE's IAQ standard for PM₁₀ concentration. As for CO₂ concentration, it was kept between 400–800 ppm, which met the KMOE's IAQ standard for CO₂ concentration (1000 ppm). The temperature of the waiting room was 27 ~ 30°C and the relative humidity was 50 ~ 80%. The radon concentration was under 70 Bq/m³. It was under 148 Bq/m³, which was the KMOE's IAQ standard for radon concentration.

A. PM₁₀ concentration

(x-axis: sampling number, y-axis: μg/m³)

B. CO₂ concentration

(x-axis: sampling number, y-axis: ppm)

C. Temperature

(x-axis: sampling number, y-axis: °C)

D. Relative Humidity

(x-axis: sampling number, y-axis: %)

E. radon concentration

(x-axis: sampling number, y-axis: Bq/m³)

Fig. 8. PM₁₀, CO₂, temperature, relative humidity, and radon concentration in the tunnel of a subway station.

III. Concluding Remarks

An air quality monitoring system based on environmental sensors were implemented to display and record the data of PM₁₀ and CO₂, temperature, humidity, and radon concentration of the tunnel of an underground subway station. In this study, an IAQ monitoring system, which uses PM₁₀ and CO₂, temperature, humidity, and radon sensor modules and a data processing module with Wi-Fi communication capabilities for the transmission and management of the measurement results, was implemented. Through these experimental studies, we believe that the implemented IAQ monitoring system would be helpful in

protecting many people from the dangers associated with indoor pollutants exposure.

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